

Physico-chemical Studies of Complex Chromium Compounds: Diethylaniline Chromithiocyanate

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In an earlier communication¹ chromithiocyanate ion has been found to combine with dimethylanilinium ion, forming a stable, rose-coloured compound. In the present communication conductometric study of the reaction between chromithiocyanate ion and diethylanilinium ion has been made. The composition of the compound formed has been discussed and absorbance of the compound in methyl ethyl ketone has been observed at different dilutions.

Procedure.—Potassium chromithiocyanate was prepared and standardised by methods adopted by Rosler² and Bjerrum³. Pure diethylaniline (B.D.H.) was redistilled and a stock solution of $M/3$ was prepared in a 200-ml volumetric flask containing 35 ml of acetic acid of sp. gr. 1.05 at 25°. Solutions of different concentrations were prepared by dilution with conductivity water.

FIG. 1

The conductivity was measured by Serfass Conductivity Bridge, Model RCM 15 B1, at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Curves A to G have been drawn in Fig. 1 between the difference in specific conductance and the fraction $[\text{diethylaniline}] / \{ [\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6^{3-}] + [\text{diethylaniline}] \}$.

Composition.—Using equimolar solutions ($M/50$) each of diethylaniline and potassium chromithiocyanate, the stoichiometry of the compound formed comes to 3:1 (Fig. 1, curve G). The diethylaniline chromithiocyanate formed is practically insoluble in water and ethanol but soluble in methyl ethyl ketone. Thus the compound was separated by filtration, washed with water, dried in air, and analysed. {Found: SCN, 41.01; Cr, 6.08. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2]_3\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6$ requires SCN, 40.95; Cr 6.11%}.

1. Gupta and Anand, unpublished.

2. *Annalen*, 1867, 141, 185.

3. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1921, 118, 131; 1922, 199, 51.

In order to study the applicability of Beer's law, the variation in optical density of diethylaniline chromithiocyanate in methyl ethyl ketone was measured at wave lengths between 380 and 600 $m\mu$ by a Hilger spectrophotometer at the room temperature (28-30°). Curves have been drawn in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

TABLE I

Solvent = methyl ethyl ketone.

Curves.	Conc. of the complex.	λ_{max} .	λ_{min} .
A'	M/500	420,560 $m\mu$	480 $m\mu$
B'	M/1000	422,558	488
C'	M/1500	418,558	490

Chromithiocyanate ion forms diethylaniline chromithiocyanate with diethylanilinium ion, similar to dimethylanilinium ion. The variation in optical density in methyl ethyl ketone and the stability of diethylaniline chromithiocyanate is very similar to that of dimethyl analogue'. There is very slight shifting in spectral maxima and minima, which may be due to dissociation of the compound in solvent by diffused day light. The composition of the compound, on the basis of conductometric curves and chemical analysis, comes as $[C_6H_5NH(C_2H_5)_2]_3 Cr (SCN)_6$.

Since diethylaniline chromithiocyanate is practically insoluble in ethanol and dimethylaniline chromithiocyanate is very soluble, the separation of diethylaniline from dimethylaniline may be easily effected with potassium chromithiocyanate.